

Inflammatory biomarker profile in optimal and suboptimal responder psoriasis patients treated with ustekinumab

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Abstract

Psoriasis is a chronic autoimmune inflammatory skin condition characterized by uncontrolled keratinocyte proliferation and potential systemic manifestations. Its pathogenesis involves activation of both innate and adaptive immune responses, leading to an imbalance in inflammatory cytokines. Interleukin (IL)-12 and IL-23 are key cytokines in the pathophysiology of psoriasis and sustain chronic skin inflammation. Biologic therapies, such as ustekinumab (UST), have been developed to induce long-term remission in moderate-to-severe psoriasis. The objective of this study was to identify differences in serum levels of inflammatory biomarkers [erythrocyte sedimentation rate, high-sensitivity C-reactive protein (hs-CRP), IL-12, IL-17, IL-22, and IL-23] between optimal and suboptimal responder Iraqi patients with moderate-to-severe plaque-type psoriasis treated with UST. Clinical response was assessed using the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) score, and patients were divided into two groups: Group 1, patients with an optimal response (PASI ≤ 3); and Group 2, patients with a suboptimal response (PASI > 3). Optimal responders demonstrated significantly greater improvement in PASI and body surface area percent change compared to suboptimal responders ($p = 0.001$ for both). In contrast, suboptimal responders exhibited significantly higher levels of hs-CRP, IL-17, IL-22, and IL-23, indicating a greater inflammatory burden among individuals with an inadequate clinical response. These findings suggest that patients with persistent disease activity have an elevated pro-inflammatory cytokine environment, which may contribute to their reduced therapeutic response. Cytokine levels may serve as crucial indicators that optimal responders achieve not only skin clearance but also deeper, systemic control of the inflammatory disease process.

Keywords

high-sensitivity C-reactive protein, interleukin-12, interleukin-17, interleukin-22, interleukin-23, psoriasis, ustekinumab

Introduction

Psoriasis (“itching condition” in the Greek language) (Al-Dhalimi et al. 2016) is a chronic autoimmune inflammatory skin condition characterized by uncontrolled keratinocyte proliferation and may extend to other systemic manifestations (Mrowietz et al. 2024). Plaque-type psori-

asis is the most common form, accounting for 85% of cases, and is characterized by sharply defined, erythematous, scaly areas or plaques that develop on the scalp, trunk, gluteal folds, knees, and elbows (Armstrong and Read 2020; Khonde et al. 2024). Other types include guttate, inverse, pustular, erythrodermic, and nail psoriasis, with different affected sites and appearances (Karim and Al-Ani 2022).

Comorbidities such as psoriatic arthritis, depression, cardiovascular disease, and hepatic disease are frequently identified and are associated with a lower quality of life (Abdulridha et al. 2020; Raharja et al. 2021; Jasim et al. 2025). Psoriasis is a multifactorial disease triggered by genetic and external stimuli, activating innate and adaptive immune responses and leading to an imbalance of inflammatory cytokines (Singh et al. 2022; Eldawoudy et al. 2024). Interleukin (IL)-12 and IL-23 are among the most commonly involved cytokines in the pathophysiology of psoriasis, inducing the differentiation and proliferation of T-helper (Th)1 and Th17 cells, respectively. Th1 cells secrete interferon gamma (IFN- γ) and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), whereas Th17 cells secrete IL-17, IL-22, and TNF- α . Among these pathways, the IL-23-mediated pathway is thought to be predominant, promoting keratinocyte activation and proliferation, which together perpetuate chronic skin inflammation (Armstrong and Read 2020; Petit et al. 2021). The choice of treatment depends on the type and severity of psoriasis. For mild to moderate psoriasis, topical medicines, phototherapy, and immunomodulators are frequently used as first-line options (Bodnár et al. 2024). Biologics have emerged and are used to induce long-term remission in moderate to severe psoriasis (Palakornkitti et al. 2021). These therapies target specific components of the immune system implicated in the pathophysiology of psoriasis (Reid and Griffiths 2020). Ustekinumab (UST) is a fully human IgG1 kappa (κ) monoclonal antibody that binds specifically to the p40 subunit shared by IL-12 and IL-23 (Olteanu et al. 2024). Blockade of the p40 subunit prevents IL-12 and IL-23 from binding to receptor complexes on T cells, thereby inhibiting downstream signaling and the production of inflammatory cytokines (Wcisło-Dziadecka et al. 2019). This inhibition reduces keratinocyte proliferation, leading to a significant decrease in skin lesions and disease severity, as measured by the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) (Jeon et al. 2017). Interleukins and C-reactive protein (CRP) are considered important markers for monitoring inflammation and therapeutic response, and their serum levels have been linked to disease activity (Siebert et al. 2019). A recent study revealed increased expression of IL-23 and IL-17, which interact with other cytokines, especially IL-12 and IL-22, promoting a self-sustaining feed-forward circuit in keratinocytes and contributing to disease chronicity (Nong et al. 2024; Kim et al. 2021). In addition, high-sensitivity C-reactive protein (hs-CRP) is now recognized as a valuable biomarker in psoriasis, with higher levels correlating with PASI scores (Amedi and Zangana 2021). The objective of this study is to identify differences in serum levels of inflammatory biomarkers [erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), hs-CRP, IL-12, IL-17, IL-22, and IL-23] between optimal and suboptimal responder Iraqi patients with moderate-to-severe plaque-type psoriasis treated with UST. These biomarkers may ultimately be used as objective, easily measurable tools for monitoring treatment effectiveness, assessing systemic inflammation, and potentially guiding treatment adjustments.

Patients, materials, and methods

Study population and design

A cross-sectional study was carried out between March 2025 and August 2025 at the Center of Dermatology and Venereology, Baghdad Teaching Hospital, Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq. A total of 75 patients were enrolled. Each participant was monitored by a specialist dermatologist and managed in accordance with the American Academy of Dermatology guidelines (Menter et al. 2019). All patients received subcutaneous UST at a dose of 90 mg, administered at weeks 0 and 4 (induction dose), and then every 12 weeks thereafter (maintenance dose). Comprehensive demographic, medical, surgical, and smoking histories were obtained, along with a review of baseline and most recent PASI and BSA scores. Age, body mass index (BMI), disease duration, and UST treatment duration were also documented.

Grouping of study participants

Patients were allocated into two groups according to clinical response (Elberdín et al. 2022):

- Group 1: Patients with an optimal response to UST therapy (PASI \leq 3).
- Group 2: Patients with a suboptimal response to UST therapy (PASI $>$ 3).

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria:

1. Age over 18 years old.
2. Patients diagnosed with moderate-to-severe plaque-type psoriasis according to PASI score (Ko et al. 2016).
3. Patients who received UST doses regularly for at least 6 months and were considered adherent according to medical records.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Patients with active infections or other autoimmune diseases, to avoid skewing ILs and hs-CRP.
2. Patients using anti-inflammatory medication in addition to UST.
3. Patients with psoriasis types other than plaque psoriasis or with concomitant skin diseases.

Blood samples and data collection

Each participant provided 5 milliliters of venous blood just before the next scheduled UST dose. Collected blood samples were centrifuged at 4,000 rpm for 10 minutes. The serum was then isolated and stored at -80°C for further analysis. Interleukin concentrations (IL-12, IL-17, IL-22,

and IL-23) were measured using commercially available sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits (*Sunlong*[®], Cat. No. SL0970Hu, SL0978Hu, SL0988Hu, and SL0989Hu, respectively, China), following the manufacturer's protocol. In addition, hs-CRP was measured using a sandwich ELISA kit (*Elabscience*[®], Cat. No. E-EL-H5134, China).

Statistical analysis

The Shapiro–Wilk test was used to assess whether variables were normally distributed. For normally distributed data, results were expressed as the mean and standard deviation (SD), and an independent *t*-test was employed to compare variables between groups. For data that did not follow a normal distribution, the median and interquartile range (IQR) were used, and the Mann–Whitney *U* test was applied to compare groups. The chi-squared test was used to compare categorical variables. All analyses were performed using SPSS version 27 (Chicago, USA), and a *p*-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The demographic and disease characteristics of the entire study sample are shown in Table 1. The majority of participants were men (69.33%), whereas women accounted for 30.67% of the sample. Participants had a mean age of 38.88 ± 13.17 years and a body mass index of 29.18 ± 4.60 kg/m². The overall median duration of psoriasis was 12 years, whereas the median duration of UST treatment was 19 months. Regarding clinical background, 37.7% of patients had a family history of psoriasis, 29.3% had undergone surgical procedures, and 22.7% had medical comorbidities. Smoking was reported by 12% of participants. The baseline PASI and BSA had median values of 19 and 31, respectively, indicating moderate to severe disease activity at enrollment.

Table 2 presents the differences in demographic and clinical characteristics between the optimal and suboptimal responder groups. The two groups were comparable in sex distribution, disease duration, and UST treatment duration. Suboptimal responders, however, were significantly older and had a higher BMI (*p* = 0.002 and *p* = 0.01, respectively). As expected, optimal responders showed markedly greater improvement in PASI and BSA percent change compared with suboptimal responders (*p* = 0.001 for both).

A comparison of the inflammatory biomarker profile between optimal and suboptimal responders is illustrated in Table 3. There were no significant differences in erythrocyte sedimentation rate or IL-12 levels between the two groups. In contrast, suboptimal responders had significantly higher levels of hs-CRP, IL-17, IL-22, and IL-23 (Fig. 1), indicating a larger inflammatory burden among individuals with an inadequate clinical response.

The receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis of the studied biomarkers across PASI groups is present-

ed in Table 4. hs-CRP showed a statistically significant predictive value, with an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.717 (95% CI: 0.601–0.815; *p* = 0.0005). IL-17 and IL-23 demonstrated the highest diagnostic performance among the cytokines, with AUC values of 0.731 and 0.723, respectively, both of which were statistically significant. Sensitivity and specificity values at the identified cut-offs further support the potential of IL-17 and IL-23 as useful markers for distinguishing optimal and suboptimal responder groups.

Discussion

In this study, serum levels of ESR, hs-CRP, and multiple interleukins (IL-12, IL-17, IL-22, and IL-23) were assessed in psoriasis patients who responded either optimally or suboptimally to UST therapy. This adds to the emerging evidence that the inflammatory biomarker profile can help explain variability in clinical response to biologics and may provide further insight into the mechanisms underlying UST efficacy. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first clinical study in Iraq to evaluate this number of biomarkers simultaneously.

Comparison of demographic and clinical characteristics between optimal and suboptimal responders (Table 2) identified age as a significant differentiator, with suboptimal responders being notably older than optimal responders. This finding aligns with a study reporting that older patients are less likely to achieve an optimal response (PASI 90) at 6 months among psoriasis patients treated with biologics, with an odds ratio of 0.99 (95% CI, 0.98–1.00), suggesting a lower therapeutic response in this population (Hjort et al. 2024). In addition, other studies showed that patients older than 65 years exhibited a slower initial response to biologics (PASI 90 and PASI < 3), but comparable long-term outcomes to younger patients (Rosset et al. 2023; Hacınecipoglu et al. 2025). In contrast, another study did not observe an age-related decline in response, suggesting that the impact of age may vary across populations and may be influenced by disease duration, cumulative treatment exposure, and baseline inflammatory activity (Sobotkova et al. 2025).

Higher BMI was also significantly associated with a suboptimal response (Table 2), consistent with previous literature showing that obesity makes improvement with biologics more difficult (Schwarz et al. 2021; Avci et al. 2024). Patients with a BMI ≥ 30 kg/m² had lower response rates, which is attributed in part to psoriasis-induced inflammation. Obese individuals have greater amounts of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF-α produced by adipose tissue, which can aggravate psoriasis severity and impair the efficacy of biological therapy. Furthermore, excess body weight may affect pharmacokinetic variables, including clearance, volume of distribution, and serum drug levels, which may contribute to decreased efficacy (Pirro et al. 2021).

Table 1. Demographic and clinical data of the study sample.

Variable	Results
(Sex) Female [n (%)]	23 (30.67%)
Male [n (%)]	52 (69.33 %)
Age (years) [mean ± SD]	38.88 ± 13.17
BMI (kg/m ²) [mean ± SD]	29.18 ± 4.60
Disease duration (years) [median (IQR)]	[12.00 (7.50–20.00)]
Ustekinumab Treatment duration (months) [median (IQR)]	[19.00 (10.00–22.00)]
Family history of psoriasis [n (%)]	[28 (37.7%)]
Surgical history [n (%)]	[22 (29.3%)]
Medical history [n (%)]	[17 (22.7%)]
Smoking history [n (%)]	[9 (12.0 %)]
PASI score [median (IQR)]	Baseline [19.00 (13.00–28.00)] Last [2.00 (1.00–4.10)]
BSA (m ²) [median (IQR)]	Baseline [34.00 (25.00–45.00)] Last [2.00 (1.00–9.50)]

BMI: body mass index; BSA: body surface area; IQR: interquartile range; PASI: Psoriasis Area and Severity Index; SD: standard deviation.

Table 2. Differences in demographic and clinical characteristics between optimal psoriatic patient responders (Group 1) and sub-optimal responders (Group 2).

Variable	Group 1	Group 2	P-value
Sex (a)			
Female [n (%)]	19 (38%)	4 (16%)	0.051
Male [n (%)]	31 (62%)	21 (84%)	
Age(year) ^(b) [mean ± SD]	35.60 ± 12.57	45.44 ± 12.02	0.002**
BMI (kg/m ²) ^(b) [mean ± SD]	28.25 ± 3.85	31.05 ± 5.45	0.012 **
Duration of disease (years) [median (IQR)] ^(c)	11 (7.00–15.00)	14(8.00–20.00)	0.242
Ustekinumab Treatment duration (months) [median (IQR)] ^(c)	17.5 (10.00–22.00)	19 (10.00–25.00)	0.916
Δ PASI score (%) ^(b)	91.03 ± 9.23	64.56 ± 20.34	0.001**
Δ BSA (%) ^(b)	91.18 ± 14.89	68.10 ± 24.85	0.001**

BMI: body mass index; BSA: body surface area; IQR: interquartile range; PASI: Psoriasis Area and Severity Index; SD: standard deviation. (*) Significant difference ($p < 0.05$). (a) Chi-square test was used for statistical analysis. (b) Two-sample t -test was used for statistical analysis. (c) Mann-Whitney U test was used for statistical analysis.

Table 3. Difference between psoriasis patients [optimal responders (Group 1) and suboptimal responders (Group 2)] according to inflammatory markers.

Variable	Group 1	Group 2	P-value
ESR (mm/hr)	12.32 ± 9.62	13.68 ± 5.42	0.513
hs-CRP(mg/L)	1.76 ± 0.62	2.24 ± 0.93	0.009 **
IL 12 (pg/ml)	10.96 ± 3.95	11.71 ± 2.91	0.462
IL 17 (pg/ml)	11.15 ± 5.19	15.05 ± 3.36	0.001**
IL22 (pg/ml)	19.23 ± 4.62	22.12 ± 5.81	0.027*
IL 23 (pg/ml)	12.27 ± 4.31	14.84 ± 2.59	0.008**

ESR: erythrocyte sedimentation rate; hs-CRP: high-sensitivity C-reactive protein; IL: interleukin. A two-sample t -test was used (data were presented as mean ± SD). (**) Highly significant difference ($p < 0.01$).

Table 4. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis.

variable	Cut-off	sensitivity	specificity	AUC	P-value	CI 95%
ESR (mm/hr)	>7	92%	42%	0.608	0.092	0.488–0.719
hs-CRP (mg/L)	>1.63	80 %	58 %	0.717	0.0005**	0.601–0.815
IL 12 (pg/ml)	>8.02	92%	32%	0.583	0.210	0.464–0.696
IL 17 (pg/ml)	>11.69	88%	52%	0.731	0.0004 **	0.597–0.811
IL22 (pg/ml)	>21.26	60%	72%	0.646	0.027 *	0.527–0.753
IL 23 (pg/ml)	>11.57	96%	52%	0.723	0.0001**	0.608–0.820

AUC: area under the curve; CI: confidence interval; Cut-off: threshold separating positive from negative results; ESR: erythrocyte sedimentation rate; hs-CRP: high-sensitivity C-reactive protein; IL: interleukin; Sensitivity: true positive cases; Specificity: true negative cases; ROC: receiver operating characteristic.

Figure 1. Box plots illustrating the distribution of inflammatory biomarkers among optimal responders (Group 1) and suboptimal responders (Group 2) with psoriasis. Panels show **A.** erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR); **B.** high-sensitivity C-reactive protein (hs-CRP); **C.** interleukin-12 (IL-12); **D.** interleukin-17 (IL-17); **E.** interleukin-22 (IL-22); and **F.** interleukin-23 (IL-23).

Disease chronicity and treatment duration did not independently predict treatment response, as indicated by the non-significant differences between groups. A real-world study showed that psoriasis duration (shorter vs. more than 2 years) does not appear to be a crucial factor in achieving optimal treatment outcomes, which are more strongly influenced by the type of biologic therapy used (Pinter et al. 2024). It has been reported that even among ultra-long-term UST users (>10 years) with PASI scores remaining below 3 from 6 months onward, total clearance was rarely achieved (3.9–13.7% at different time points). This suggests that an effective, although not optimal, response may be maintained with continued use (Henckens et al. 2025). Specific characteristics, such as HLA-C*06 positivity, female sex, biologic-naïve status, and BMI <30 kg/m², were associated with improved PASI response after 2 years, regardless of disease duration or treatment length (Galluzzo et al. 2020; Chiu et al. 2023). The significantly greater improvements in PASI and BSA percentages observed among optimal responders confirm that the clinical classification applied in this study meaningfully reflects treatment efficacy. These findings are consistent with prior studies demonstrating that patients achieving PASI < 3 or similar thresholds experience greater reductions in skin involvement and overall disease burden (Strober et al. 2025).

The variability in treatment outcomes, despite comparable treatment duration, underscores the multifactorial nature of UST response and highlights the importance of inflammatory profiling. Significantly higher levels of several inflammatory biomarkers, particularly hs-CRP, IL-17, IL-22, and IL-23, were observed in suboptimal responders (PASI > 3) compared with optimal responders. A previous

study demonstrated that hs-CRP levels were significantly correlated with psoriasis severity, with patients with moderate to severe psoriasis (PASI > 10) exhibiting higher mean serum hs-CRP levels (6.96 ± 4.18 mg/L) than those with mild disease (PASI < 10; 3.12 ± 1.90 mg/L) (Amedi and Zangana 2021). This association has led to the proposal that hs-CRP may serve as a biomarker of overall inflammation, reflecting both skin severity and cardiovascular risk in psoriasis (Uaratanawong et al. 2016). ESR levels were comparable between groups (Table 3) and showed no direct association with PASI, despite being elevated in psoriasis patients compared with healthy controls, as reported previously (Şener et al. 2023). Both ESR and CRP are classical acute-phase markers and should be interpreted cautiously, as ESR is more informative in infectious conditions, whereas CRP is more responsive in inflammatory disorders (Singh et al. 2018).

The elevation of IL-23 and IL-17 in suboptimal responders suggests that these cytokines are indicative of an incomplete clinical response, even when other inflammatory markers have normalized (Sabri and Ibraheem 2024). These findings are consistent with the established role of the IL-23/IL-17 axis in psoriasis pathogenesis, in which enhanced activation of this pathway correlates with disease persistence and reduced therapeutic response (Gargiulo et al. 2024; Gao et al. 2025).

The absence of significant differences in IL-12 levels observed in this study contrasts with findings from studies reporting a strong correlation between IL-12 levels and PASI scores (Abbas and Mousa 2022). This discrepancy may reflect the immunopathogenesis of psoriasis, which shifts from a Th1-mediated initiation phase—character-

ized by IL-12—to a Th17-driven maintenance phase—characterized by IL-23—in chronic plaques. Consequently, IL-12 levels may become dissociated from disease severity in established disease (Wang et al. 2025).

Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting these results. First, the biomarkers examined have not yet been validated in large, independent cohorts. Future research in well-defined, prospective cohorts is required before these biomarkers can be applied in routine clinical practice. Second, systemic inflammatory biomarker levels were assessed only at the study endpoint because of the original study design and resource constraints. The absence of baseline data precluded evaluation of changes in the inflammatory profile during UST treatment. Future prospective studies incorporating longitudinal measurements from baseline are warranted to further elucidate the dynamic relationship between systemic inflammation and clinical outcomes.

Conclusion

The observed pattern of findings indicates that inflammatory biomarkers, including hs-CRP, IL-17, IL-22, and IL-23, have the potential to serve as objective, easily measurable tools for monitoring treatment effectiveness, assessing systemic inflammation, and potentially guiding treatment adjustments. Differences in these biomarkers may act as crucial indicators that optimal responders achieve not only skin clearance but also deeper, systemic control of the inflammatory disease process.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The study was approved by the Scientific and Ethical Committee at the College of Pharmacy, University of Baghdad (approval name: REC062444H, date 20/10/2024). Before sample collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

AI-assisted tools (QuillBot and Grammarly) were used to support language editing during manuscript preparation. These tools assisted with paraphrasing for clarity, correcting grammar and spelling, and improving readability. No AI tools were used to generate original scientific content, analyze data, or draw conclusions.

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Author contributions

The authors' contributions are as follows: the second author conceived and designed the study; the first and third authors collected the data; and the first and second authors prepared the draft manuscript. All authors evaluated the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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